

Graphene Nanosheets: A Review on Synthesis, Characterization, and Electrode Performance

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ABSTRACT

Graphene nanosheets (GNS) have emerged as a promising material in advanced energy storage and conversion technologies due to their exceptional electrical conductivity, high surface area, mechanical strength, and electrochemical stability. This review provides a comprehensive overview of recent advancements in the synthesis, characterization, and application of graphene nanosheets, with a particular focus on their performance as electrode materials. Various synthesis techniques, including chemical vapor deposition (CVD), liquid-phase exfoliation, chemical reduction, and electrochemical methods, are discussed in detail, highlighting their advantages, limitations, and scalability. The review also explores key characterization methods, such as Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning and transmission electron microscopy (SEM/TEM), and atomic force microscopy (AFM), that are employed to assess the structural and morphological properties of GNS. Furthermore, the electrochemical performance of graphene nanosheets in applications such as supercapacitors, lithium-ion batteries, and fuel cells is critically analyzed. The influence of synthesis route, structural defects, functionalization, and composite formation on electrode behavior is examined to provide insights into the design of high-performance GNS-based electrodes. Finally, the challenges and prospects for the practical implementation of graphene nanosheets in commercial energy storage devices are outlined.

Keywords: Graphene nanosheets, rGO, CVD, XRD, SEM, TEM, EIS.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The technological importance of graphene nanosheets (GNs) lies in their ability to bridge fundamental nanoscience with practical applications. In energy storage, graphene's ultrahigh conductivity and large surface area facilitate rapid electron transport and high charge storage capacity, making it an ideal electrode material for supercapacitors, lithium-ion batteries, and emerging sodium- and potassium-ion storage systems [1].

In electronics, the ballistic transport properties and flexibility of GNSs have driven interest in high-frequency transistors, flexible displays, and transparent conductive films. Biomedical applications, such as drug delivery, biosensing, and tissue engineering, exploit graphene's biocompatibility and ease of functionalization with biomolecules[2]. Furthermore, graphene-based membranes are being engineered for advanced water purification and gas separation, leveraging their tunable permeability and high mechanical strength.

Graphene nanosheets (GNSs) are two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterials composed of single or few-layered sheets of sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms arranged in a honeycomb lattice [3]. Since the isolation of monolayer graphene by Novoselov and Geim in 2004, GNSs have garnered immense attention due to their remarkable electrical, mechanical, thermal, and chemical properties [4]. Unlike bulk graphite, GNSs exhibit a high specific surface area ($> 2600 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), superior electron mobility ($\sim 200,000 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$), and quantum confinement effects that enable tunable band structures [5]. These properties make them highly suitable for energy storage, catalysis, sensors, and optoelectronic devices.

The structural versatility of graphene nanosheets arises from their edge configurations, surface defects, and degree of functionalization, which significantly influence their performance in various applications. However, challenges remain in achieving large-scale, cost-effective synthesis with controlled morphology, defect density, and reproducibility. Methods such as

chemical vapor deposition (CVD), liquid-phase exfoliation, and chemical reduction of graphene oxide have been extensively studied, yet each comes with trade-offs between scalability, structural quality, and environmental impact [6]. Thus, an in-depth review of synthesis strategies, characterization approaches, and electrode performance is crucial for advancing their technological applications.

The primary objectives of this review are:

- To provide a comprehensive overview of graphene nanosheet synthesis techniques, focusing on their advantages, limitations, and scalability for industrial applications.
- To examine characterization methods used to study the structural, morphological, and electrochemical properties of graphene nanosheets.
- To evaluate the performance of graphene nanosheets as electrode materials, particularly in energy storage devices such as supercapacitors and lithium-ion batteries.
- To highlight current challenges and future directions in optimizing graphene nanosheet production for commercial use.

2. EVALUATION OF STUDIES ON GRAPHENE NANOSHEETS

Several studies have explored the research on graphene nanosheets. This study evaluates a pair of articles that establish recent developments on graphene nanosheets. Ghosh examined the potential of graphene nanosheets (GNS) in fuel cell applications, with emphasis on their structural, electrochemical, and catalytic properties [7]. The chapter adopted a comprehensive review approach, synthesizing findings from experimental and theoretical studies on graphene synthesis techniques such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD), chemical exfoliation, and reduction of graphene oxide. The results highlighted that GNS possess large surface area, high electron mobility, and tunable surface chemistry, which make them excellent supports for metal

catalysts in fuel cells. Specifically, their use enhanced oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) activity, catalyst dispersion, durability, and overall energy conversion efficiency compared to traditional carbon supports. The review also reported advances in metal-free graphene-based catalysts, which demonstrated promising performance in reducing cost and mitigating catalyst degradation.

Pandey and colleagues investigated the conversion of plastic waste into graphene nanosheets (GNS) for application in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) and supercapacitors, addressing both energy and environmental challenges [8]. The researchers employed a controlled pyrolysis process followed by chemical exfoliation to synthesize GNS from plastic waste, which were then characterized using XRD, TEM, SEM, Raman spectroscopy, and BET surface analysis to confirm their layered morphology, crystallinity, and high surface area. The results demonstrated a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 8.1% in DSSCs, which was comparable to platinum-based counter electrodes, and a specific capacitance of 472 F/g at 1 A/g for supercapacitors, with stable cycling performance over 5,000 cycles.

Jin and colleagues investigated the synergistic properties of atomically coupled two-dimensional (2D) inorganic nanosheets and graphene nanosheets as hybrid building blocks for multifunctional nanomaterials [9]. The study employed a solution-based assembly and interfacial coupling strategy to synthesize well-ordered nanohybrids, which were extensively characterized using XRD, TEM, AFM, Raman spectroscopy, and XPS to confirm atomic-level integration and structural stability. Results demonstrated that the hybrid nanosheets exhibited enhanced electrical conductivity, mechanical flexibility, and catalytic activity compared to individual components, owing to strong interfacial interactions that improved charge transfer and stability.

Sabito and colleagues explored the synergistic effect of thermal and chemical reduction of graphene oxide (GO) on the performance of dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) by fabricating counter

electrodes with improved conductivity and catalytic activity [10]. The study employed a two-step reduction process, where GO films were first chemically reduced using hydrazine hydrate and then subjected to thermal annealing at various temperatures. The structural, morphological, and electrochemical properties of the reduced GO (rGO) films were characterized using XRD, Raman spectroscopy, SEM, TEM, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Performance tests of the DSSCs revealed that the combined thermal and chemical reduction enhanced electron transport, catalytic activity for I_3^-/I^- redox reactions, and overall device stability. The optimized rGO counter electrode achieved a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 7.32%, closely approaching that of platinum-based electrodes (7.86%).

Yoon and Jung developed polycarbonate–graphene nanocomposites by grafting polycarbonate onto graphene nanosheets to enhance performance in electrostatic discharge (ESD) and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding applications [11]. The grafting process improved dispersion and interfacial bonding between the graphene and polymer matrix, leading to superior mechanical strength, thermal stability, and electrical conductivity. Characterization results revealed that the composites displayed uniform morphology and improved structural integrity, which directly contributed to their functional performance. The nanocomposites exhibited significant improvements in EMI shielding effectiveness and static charge dissipation compared to pure polycarbonate.

Kazemi and coauthors studied the development of binder-free electrodes composed of $NiMoO_4$ /graphene oxide (GO) nanosheets to enhance supercapacitor performance [12]. The electrodes were fabricated via a hydrothermal synthesis route, where $NiMoO_4$ nanostructures were directly grown on graphene oxide nanosheets without the use of polymer binders. Structural and morphological characterization through XRD, SEM, TEM, Raman spectroscopy, and BET surface

analysis confirmed the successful integration of NiMoO₄ with GO, forming a porous, conductive network. Electrochemical performance was evaluated using cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), which revealed a specific capacitance of 1,217 F/g at 1 A/g, excellent rate capability, and long-term cycling stability with 92% capacitance retention after 5,000 cycles. The results showed that the integrated combination of NiMoO₄ and GO enhanced ion diffusion, conductivity, and electroactive surface area [12].

He and colleagues developed a layered-template nanospace-confinement strategy to produce corrugated graphene nanosheets (CGNS) from petroleum pitch for high-performance supercapacitor applications [13]. The synthesis involved intercalating petroleum pitch into layered templates, followed by carbonization and template removal, resulting in thin graphene sheets with corrugated morphology. Characterization using XRD, SEM, TEM, Raman spectroscopy, and BET surface-area analysis confirmed a high degree of graphitization, large surface area, and porous nanosheet structure. Electrochemical testing with cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) showed that the CGNS exhibited a specific capacitance of 245 F/g at 1 A/g, excellent rate capability, and long cycling stability with 92% retention after 5,000 cycles. The corrugated structure was found to prevent sheet restacking, enhance electrolyte ion diffusion, and improve conductivity.

Thirumal and coauthors reported a single-pot electrochemical synthesis approach for producing functionalized and phosphorus-doped graphene nanosheets aimed for supercapacitor applications [14]. The method allowed simultaneous exfoliation, functionalization, and heteroatom doping, resulting in nanosheets with improved surface area, electrical conductivity, and defect sites favorable for charge storage. Structural and morphological analyses confirmed successful phosphorus incorporation and uniform graphene sheet formation. Electrochemical testing

demonstrated that the doped nanosheets exhibited enhanced specific capacitance, superior cyclic stability, and excellent charge–discharge reversibility compared to undoped graphene.

Zhu and colleagues reported the synthesis of ultrathin nickel hydroxide and oxide nanosheets for supercapacitor applications [15]. Using a controlled synthesis strategy, they obtained nanosheets with large surface area, high porosity, and uniform morphology, which are favorable for electrochemical energy storage. Detailed characterization confirmed the ultrathin layered structure that facilitated rapid ion transport and efficient charge storage. Electrochemical performance tests revealed high specific capacitance, excellent rate capability, and superior cycling stability, highlighting the advantages of the nanosheet architecture.

Zhang and colleagues studied the synthesized SnS₂/reduced graphene oxide (rGO) nanocomposites to evaluate their efficiency in lithium-ion storage applications [16]. The integration of SnS₂ with rGO improved the electrochemical properties by enhancing conductivity and buffering the volume changes during charge–discharge cycles. Structural and electrochemical analyses revealed that the nanocomposites exhibited high reversible capacity, excellent cycling stability, and superior rate capability compared to pure SnS₂ electrodes. The rGO matrix provided a conductive framework that facilitated electron transport and accommodated strain, thereby preventing electrode pulverization.

Fang and coauthors investigated the synthesis of two-dimensional mesoporous carbon nanosheets and their transformation into graphene nanosheets for application in lithium-ion battery (LIB) anodes [16]. The study employed an evaporation-induced self-assembly (EISA) method using block copolymers as templates to fabricate ordered mesoporous carbon nanosheets, which were subsequently thermally treated to obtain graphene nanosheets. Characterization techniques such as XRD, TEM, SEM, Raman spectroscopy, and nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms confirmed

the high surface area, mesoporous structure, and thin-layered morphology. Electrochemical evaluations using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) demonstrated that the graphene nanosheets exhibited an exceptionally high reversible capacity of 1,043 mAh/g at 0.1 A/g, excellent rate performance, and long-term cycling stability over 500 cycles. The results highlighted that the mesoporous architecture provided abundant ion diffusion channels, while the thin graphene layers enhanced conductivity and structural stability.

Sathish and colleagues investigated the synthesis and application of ultrathin SnS₂ nanoparticles grown on graphene nanosheets for lithium-ion storage [17]. Using a simple solution-based method, SnS₂ nanoparticles were uniformly anchored onto graphene nanosheets to prevent particle agglomeration and enhance conductivity. The hybrid nanostructure was characterized through XRD, TEM, SEM, and Raman spectroscopy, confirming the homogeneous distribution of SnS₂ on graphene layers. Electrochemical tests revealed that the SnS₂/graphene composite exhibited a high reversible capacity of 620 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.1C, superior to bare SnS₂, with improved cycling stability and rate performance due to graphene's role in buffering volume changes during charge/discharge cycles.

3. SYNTHESIS OF GRAPHENE NANOSHEETS

There have been several strategic techniques used to synthesize graphene nanosheets. Fan and Shen [18] outlined several approaches for synthesizing graphene nanosheets, including chemical vapor deposition (CVD), liquid-phase exfoliation, mechanical exfoliation, hydrothermal/solvothermal methods, and reduction of graphene oxide. Authors have emphasised that the choice of synthesis method significantly impacts the structural and electrocatalytic properties of graphene nanosheets utilised in energy conversion [7, 13, 18]. CVD yielded high-quality graphene with excellent crystallinity, it was costly and challenging to scale; liquid-phase and mechanical exfoliation provided simpler routes but suffered from low yields and inconsistent sheet sizes. Hydrothermal

and solvothermal methods offered one-pot strategies for porous nanosheets [18]. Still, they often resulted in structural defects, whereas chemical reduction of graphene oxide provided a cost-effective alternative but left residual oxygen groups that diminished conductivity.

One of the common ones is chemical vapor deposition. According to Ghosh [7], chemical vapor deposition (CVD) was highlighted for producing high-quality nanosheets with excellent crystallinity, although its complexity and high cost limited industrial use. The approach offered a scalable and cost-effective route, taking advantage of petroleum pitch as a cheap carbon source, while overcoming limitations of conventional chemical vapor deposition (CVD) or chemical reduction methods [13]. Liquid-phase exfoliation was presented as a more scalable approach, offering moderate quality nanosheets at larger yields, while the reduction of graphene oxide (GO) provided cost-effective production, albeit with residual oxygen functionalities that impaired conductivity[7].

Hydrothermal and solvothermal methods were also discussed as versatile, low-cost techniques for producing porous nanosheets, which are particularly valuable for catalytic activity in fuel cells.[7, 12] Additionally, an incorporated technique is the reduction methods, which leave oxygen functional groups or structural defects that limit conductivity, where a reduced graphene oxide (rGO) is obtained [10]. The synthesis begins with the preparation of GO by a modified Hummers' method, followed by thermal treatment at controlled temperatures and subsequent chemical reduction using hydrazine hydrate, yielding highly conductive and catalytically active rGO nanosheets [10]. Kazemi, et al. [12] also synthesized graphene nanosheets via a facile hydrothermal route, where NiMoO₄ nanorods were directly grown on GO nanosheets without the need for polymer binders. This method enhanced the active material–substrate interaction, creating a highly conductive and mechanically stable hybrid electrode [12]. The intimate coupling between NiMoO₄

and GO provided an interconnected network that facilitated electron transport and ion accessibility, critical for energy storage applications [12].

Zhu, et al. [15] developed a novel approach for synthesizing ultrathin nickel hydroxide [Ni(OH)₂] and nickel oxide (NiO) nanosheets through a facile solution-based method followed by controlled thermal treatment. Also, Sathish, et al. [17] applied a solution-based chemical route, in which ultrathin SnS₂ nanoparticles were directly anchored onto graphene nanosheets. The synthesis strategy was designed to achieve nanosheets with large surface areas, reduced thickness, and excellent porosity, which are highly favorable for charge storage applications [15, 17]. The thin-layered morphology aimed to enhance ion diffusion, surface redox reactions, and overall electrochemical performance when employed in supercapacitors [15]. This approach ensured uniform distribution of nanoparticles, effectively preventing particle agglomeration and improving electrochemical accessibility [17]. The graphene nanosheets provided a conductive scaffold, while the ultrathin SnS₂ offered high theoretical lithium storage capacity, making the composite a promising anode material.

He, et al. [13] introduced a layered-template-nanospace-confinement strategy to produce corrugated graphene nanosheets from petroleum pitch. This method utilized layered templates to restrict the growth and expansion of graphene precursors, creating nanosheets with controlled corrugation and high structural integrity [13]. .

Pandey, et al. [8] innovated a novel waste-to-energy approach by synthesizing graphene nanosheets from plastic waste, providing both an eco-friendly recycling solution and a sustainable material source for energy devices. The process involved pyrolysis of plastic waste to produce carbonaceous material, followed by chemical treatments and exfoliation steps to obtain few-layer graphene nanosheets [8]. This approach not only offered a cost-effective route to graphene production but

also addressed the pressing issue of plastic pollution by converting non-biodegradable waste into high-value nanomaterials.

Jin, et al. [9] studied the coupling of atomically thin 2D inorganic nanosheets with graphene nanosheets to develop versatile nanohybrids. Their synthesis strategy relied on controlled self-assembly and coupling at the atomic scale, enabling intimate interfacial contact between the inorganic layers and graphene [9]. This atomically coupled configuration effectively combined the unique properties of each component: the high electrical conductivity and flexibility of graphene with the functional, tunable chemistry of 2D inorganic materials such as transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) and layered oxides [9].

Yoon and Jung [11] developed a grafting method to covalently attach polycarbonate chains onto graphene nanosheets, thereby creating high-performance polycarbonate-graphene nanocomposites. The grafting was achieved through a surface-initiated polymerization approach, designed to overcome the common issue of poor compatibility and dispersion of graphene in polymer matrices [11]. By chemically bonding polycarbonate chains to graphene, the study sought to improve interfacial interactions, structural integrity, and the overall performance of polymer nanocomposites.

Thirumal, et al. [14] established a single-pot electrochemical synthesis method for producing functionalized and phosphorus-doped graphene nanosheets aimed at enhancing energy storage applications. The electrochemical approach was designed to be a cost-effective, scalable, and environmentally friendly route compared to conventional chemical reduction or thermal treatment processes [14]. Incorporating phosphorus into the graphene lattice was intended to introduce additional redox-active sites, enhance surface functionality, and improve the overall electrochemical performance of graphene for supercapacitors [14].

Zhang, et al. [16] innovated a strategy to combine the high theoretical lithium storage capacity of SnS₂ with the excellent electrical conductivity and structural flexibility of RGO. By anchoring SnS₂ nanoparticles uniformly onto graphene nanosheets, the study sought to mitigate common drawbacks of SnS₂, such as large volume expansion and poor cycling stability, which typically hinder its use as an anode material in lithium-ion batteries [16].

Fang, et al. [19] developed a strategy to synthesize two-dimensional mesoporous carbon nanosheets and their derived graphene nanosheets through a hard-templating approach combined with subsequent thermal treatment. The mesoporous sheets served as a precursor framework for graphene-like structures, enabling control over thickness, porosity, and surface area [19]. Compared to conventional methods such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD) or liquid-phase exfoliation, this templating method offered improved structural uniformity and porosity, which are advantageous for electrochemical applications [19].

4. CHARACTERIZATION OF GRAPHENE NANOSHEETS

The characterization of graphene nanosheets (GNS) relies on a suite of complementary techniques. The characterization of graphene nanosheets (GNS) and their hybrids has been consistently approached through a combination of structural, morphological, spectroscopic, and electrochemical analyses.

Across various studies, X-ray diffraction (XRD) consistently served as a primary tool for confirming the crystalline or layered graphitic structures of GNS and their hybrids. For instance, Ghosh [7] and Pandey, et al. [8] highlighted the role of XRD in validating the crystalline nature and layered morphology, while Jin, et al. [9] extended this to confirm structural integration in graphene–inorganic hybrids. Similarly, Sahito, et al. [10] and Yoon and Jung [11] employed XRD

to verify exfoliation and stacking behavior within reduced graphene oxide (rGO) and nanocomposite systems, respectively.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) emerged as the most fundamental structural characterization tool across studies. It was used to confirm the crystalline phases of various hybrid materials, such as NiMoO₄ on GO (Kazemi et al.), SnS₂-RGO (Zhang et al.), and SnS₂-graphene composites (Sathish et al.) [12, 16, 17]. Similarly, Thirumal et al. confirmed successful reduction of GO alongside phosphorus incorporation, while Zhu et al. identified phase transitions of Ni(OH)₂ to NiO [14, 15]. In most cases, XRD validated crystallinity and interlayer spacing, confirming nanosheet integrity after doping or hybridization.

Microscopy techniques such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were indispensable for visualizing nanosheet morphology, surface defects, and layer alignment. Ghosh and Pandey et al. used TEM and SEM to confirm nanoscale thickness and layered sheet structures, while Jin et al. demonstrated ultrathin hybrid layers with atomic-level coupling [7-9]. SEM in particular revealed morphological changes in rGO (Sahito et al.) and uniform dispersion of graphene in polymer matrices (Yoon & Jung), emphasizing the importance of controlling agglomeration in composite materials [10, 11]. Additionally, Kazemi et al. reported uniform NiMoO₄ nanorods anchored on GO, whereas Zhang et al. and Sathish et al. observed homogeneous SnS₂ nanoparticle dispersion on graphene, ensuring conductive frameworks [12, 16, 17]. He et al. demonstrated corrugated, wrinkled nanosheets formed via nanospace confinement, while Thirumal et al. and Fang et al. reported porous and mesoporous morphologies favorable for ion transport [13, 14, 19].

Spectroscopic analyses, particularly Raman spectroscopy, provided structural disorder and bonding information. Characteristic D and G bands were observed across studies, with varying D/G ratios

indicating defect density and restoration of sp^2 domains. For instance, He et al. reported increased disorder from corrugation, while Thirumal et al. and Sathish et al. confirmed defect healing and interactions with dopants or nanoparticles [13, 14, 17]. Fang et al. further highlighted how Raman analysis linked defect density to conductivity–reactivity balance [19]. In hybrid systems, Raman spectra also revealed interfacial bonding effects, as seen in Kazemi, et al. [12] and Zhang, et al. [16]. Pandey et al. (2021) and Sahito et al. (2019) used Raman spectra to confirm partial defect restoration in rGO, while Jin et al. (2021) leveraged it to track interfacial charge transfer within hybrid systems. Similarly, Yoon & Jung (2017) observed preservation of graphitic domains despite covalent functionalization

Finally, functional property evaluations were central to bridging structure with application. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) revealed enhanced conductivity in $NiMoO_4$ –GO hybrids due to synergistic effects [12]. Electrical and mechanical tests (Fang et al.; Fan & Shen; Sahito et al.) demonstrated flexibility, tensile strength, and stability under cycling, underscoring the practical potential of GNS in flexible energy devices [10, 12, 19]. Optical methods such as UV-Vis spectroscopy (Fang et al.; Fan & Shen; Sahito et al.) further confirmed dispersion quality and electronic transitions, complementing structural findings [10, 12, 19]. Functional performance characterization was also emphasized, particularly through electrical conductivity tests.

5. APPLICATION OF GRAPHENE NANOSHEETS ON ELECTRODE PERFORMANCE

Graphene nanosheets have emerged as a transformative material in electrochemical energy devices due to their exceptional conductivity, large surface area, and structural adaptability. Comparative reports highlight their ability to enhance electrode performance across diverse applications. Graphene nanosheets and their hybrid derivatives have consistently demonstrated superior

performance as electrode materials, largely owing to their tunable morphology, structural flexibility, and conductive networks.

Early studies such as Sathish, et al. [17] revealed that SnS₂–graphene nanocomposites outperformed pristine SnS₂ in lithium-ion battery (LIB) anodes, where graphene’s conductivity and mechanical resilience buffered volume changes during lithiation/delithiation and prevented electrode pulverization. This synergistic effect was later reaffirmed by [16], who showed that SnS₂/RGO composites achieved higher reversible capacity, excellent cycling stability, and improved rate performance compared to pure SnS₂ or RGO. Both works highlight graphene’s essential role in stabilizing conversion-type anodes that typically suffer from severe volume expansion.

Beyond hybrid systems, morphology-controlled nanosheets also yielded notable performance gains. Zhu, et al. [15] demonstrated that ultrathin Ni(OH)₂ and NiO nanosheets delivered exceptionally high capacitance, superior rate capability, and long-term cycling stability relative to bulk or thicker electrodes. Their nanoscale thickness promoted ion accessibility, accelerated electron transport, and maximized redox-active surface area, underscoring the importance of nanosheet engineering in supercapacitor electrodes. Similarly, Fang, et al. [19] reported that mesoporous graphene nanosheets significantly outperformed conventional graphite in lithium-ion storage. Their interconnected mesoporous channels facilitated rapid Li⁺ diffusion, while the conductive framework ensured efficient charge transfer, resulting in enhanced specific capacity, outstanding rate performance, and robust cycling stability.

Ghosh [7] and Fan and Shen [18] emphasized their role as high-surface-area, conductive supports for platinum nanoparticles in fuel cells, where they improved catalyst dispersion and utilization.

This directly translated into enhanced oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) activity, with notable improvements in onset potential, half-wave potential, and Tafel slope compared to conventional carbon support [7, 18]. When used as counter electrodes in DSSCs, graphene facilitated faster electron transfer and reduced recombination losses, leading to superior power conversion efficiency and fuel efficiency relative to traditional Pt-based electrodes [7, 8]. Consistent with these findings, Sahito, et al. [10] specifically highlighted the advantage of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) as a counter electrode in DSSCs. The hybrid-rGO system displayed superior catalytic activity for the iodide/triiodide redox reaction [10].

Beyond energy systems, graphene–inorganic nanosheet hybrids offered potential in flexible electronics and sensing applications, where mechanical robustness and electrochemical responsiveness are equally critical. Jin, et al. [9] established that graphene–inorganic nanosheet hybrids based on a synergistic combination of graphene’s conductivity with the functional selectivity of inorganic nanosheets significantly enhanced catalytic activity for hydrogen evolution reactions (HER), improved charge transport, and provided superior capacity in energy storage devices.

In parallel, Pandey et al. (2021) demonstrated the versatility of graphene nanosheets in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) and supercapacitors. The improved electron transfer efficiency led to higher power conversion efficiencies compared to electrodes made of GO, singly reduced GO, or even costly platinum. This not only demonstrated the electrochemical superiority of graphene-based materials but also validated their potential to provide cost-effective alternatives to precious-metal electrodes. Taken together, these studies confirm that graphene nanosheets, whether in pure, hybrid, or reduced forms, substantially enhance electrode performance across multiple

electrochemical platforms [8, 10]. Their ability to support electrocatalysts, improve charge and ion transport, and maintain structural stability positions them as highly versatile and scalable materials for next-generation energy conversion and storage devices.

For supercapacitors, the nanosheets delivered high capacitance and excellent cycling stability owing to their large electrochemically active surface area and rapid ion diffusion channels [8]. These results validated the dual applicability of graphene in both photovoltaic and electrochemical storage technologies. Kazemi, et al. [12] showed that NiMoO₄/GO nanosheet hybrids outperformed pristine NiMoO₄ electrodes by leveraging graphene oxide as a conductive scaffold to facilitate rapid electron transfer, while the NiMoO₄ nanorods contributed pseudocapacitance. Similarly, He, et al. [13] highlighted how corrugated graphene nanosheets prevented restacking, thereby enhancing ion diffusion pathways and charge transport efficiency. The resulting corrugated electrodes displayed high capacitance, excellent rate performance, and long-term cycling stability, outperforming flat graphene nanosheets. Extending this, Thirumal, et al. [14] demonstrated that phosphorus doping further advanced graphene's supercapacitor performance by introducing redox-active sites and improving wettability, thereby enhancing conductivity, capacitance, and charge retention. These findings consistently position graphene nanosheets and their modifications as strong candidates for high-performance supercapacitors.

Yoon and Jung [11] explored their application in electrostatic discharge (ESD) and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding, where grafted nanocomposites achieved lower percolation thresholds and superior electrical conductivity compared to physically blended systems. The improved interfacial adhesion not only enabled efficient charge transport but also reinforced mechanical durability, making them highly suitable for electronic packaging and protective coatings.

Taken together, these comparative findings underscore the unique properties of graphene nanosheets, tunable conductivity, structural flexibility, and surface functionality. These attributes enable graphene to enhance electrode performance across supercapacitors, lithium-ion batteries, fuel cells, and electronic shielding materials. Modifications such as doping (Thirumal et al.), hybridization with metal oxides (Kazemi et al.), or structural engineering like corrugation (He et al.) further expand their application potential. This body of evidence confirms that graphene nanosheets are not only versatile but also adaptable to the specific performance demands of diverse energy storage and electronic systems.

6. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Despite the remarkable electrochemical performance and electrical efficiency of graphene nanosheets, their widespread application as electrode materials is constrained by several challenges. A major limitation lies in the tendency of nanosheets to restack or agglomerate due to strong π - π interactions and van der Waals forces [15-17]. This restacking reduces the accessible surface area, hinders electrolyte penetration, and limits ion diffusion, thereby diminishing the theoretical advantages of graphene's two-dimensional structure. While strategies such as corrugation (He et al.) or mesoporous structuring (Fang et al.) alleviate this issue, scalable solutions remain underdeveloped [13, 19].

Another challenge is the control of defect density and functionalization. Although defects and heteroatom doping can enhance active sites and pseudocapacitance (Thirumal et al.), excessive structural disorder compromises electrical conductivity and mechanical stability [14]. Achieving an optimal balance between conductivity and defect-induced activity is still difficult, particularly in large-scale synthesis.

The cost and scalability of high-quality graphene production also pose significant hurdles. Many reported methods, including chemical vapor deposition (CVD), hydrothermal synthesis, and templating approaches, are expensive, energy-intensive, or lack reproducibility at industrial scales [7, 12, 18]. Chemical exfoliation and reduction of graphene oxide are more scalable but often leave residual oxygen groups or structural defects that reduce performance compared to pristine graphene nanosheets [7, 18].

Furthermore, long-term cycling stability and mechanical degradation during repeated lithiation/delithiation cycles remain concerns, especially in lithium-ion batteries [3, 11, 13]. Although graphene can buffer volume changes of metal oxides or sulfides, continuous expansion–contraction cycles may still induce stress and eventual electrode failure over extended operation.

In summary, the main challenges of graphene nanosheets in electrode applications are:

1. Restacking and agglomeration reduce ion/electron accessibility.
2. The scalability of synthesis remained limited, especially for CVD-grown nanosheets, which are expensive and difficult to mass-produce.
3. Stability and durability in electrochemical systems were also noted as concerns, as nanosheets often degrade under repeated cycling.
4. Environmental risks associated with chemical reduction agents, along with high production costs, further hindered industrial adoption.
5. Integration into practical device architectures was described as another bottleneck due to challenges in controlling sheet alignment and contact resistance.

7. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND EMERGING TRENDS

To overcome the existing challenges of graphene nanosheets (GNS) in electrode applications, several research directions are currently being pursued and require further exploration.

- 1. Preventing Restacking and Enhancing Surface Accessibility:** Future efforts should focus on developing **three-dimensional (3D) graphene architectures** (aerogels, foams, and porous frameworks) that maintain high surface area while minimizing nanosheet restacking. For instance, mesoporous graphene nanosheets (Fang et al., 2013) have shown excellent lithium-ion diffusion and cycling stability. Scalable fabrication of such hierarchical structures will be critical for commercial viability.
- 2. Controlled Defect Engineering and Doping:** Defects and heteroatom doping (e.g., N, P, S, B) can enhance pseudocapacitance and ion adsorption, but excessive structural damage reduces conductivity. Future research should emphasize precise defect control and rational doping strategies, possibly through plasma treatments, atomic layer deposition (ALD), or molecular precursors. Optimizing defect density while preserving electrical pathways could lead to higher-performance electrodes.
- 3. Low-Cost, Scalable, and Green Synthesis Methods:** Large-scale and cost-effective synthesis remains a bottleneck. Advances in biomass-derived graphene, electrochemical exfoliation, and template-free self-assembly methods are promising directions. Developing eco-friendly and energy-efficient synthesis routes that balance quality with scalability will be essential for industrial adoption.
- 4. Improved Structural Stability During Cycling:** To mitigate capacity fading caused by

mechanical degradation, researchers are exploring flexible graphene hybrids with metals, oxides, sulfides, and polymers. Future studies should focus on self-healing composites or mechanically adaptive graphene frameworks that can withstand prolonged charge–discharge cycles without structural collapse.

5. **Interfacial Engineering in Graphene-Based Composites:** The performance of graphene–nanoparticle composites depend heavily on interfacial contact. Emerging research in covalent bonding, surface functionalization, and in-situ growth techniques may enable stronger, more uniform nanoparticle anchoring. This will improve electron/ion transport pathways, minimize agglomeration, and enhance long-term stability.
6. **Integration into Next-Generation Devices:** Beyond lithium-ion batteries and supercapacitors, GNS research should expand toward sodium-ion batteries, lithium–sulfur batteries, solid-state batteries, and fuel cells. Graphene nanosheets' high conductivity and structural flexibility make them ideal candidates for these emerging energy technologies. Additionally, integrating GNS into flexible and wearable energy storage systems could open pathways for next-generation electronics.

8. CONCLUSION

The reviewed studies demonstrate that the synthesis, characterization and electrochemical application of graphene nanosheets and their hybrids requires a comprehensive, multi-technique approach to fully capture their structural, morphological, and functional attributes. Core techniques such as XRD, SEM, TEM, and Raman spectroscopy remain indispensable for confirming crystallinity, nanosheet architecture, and defect levels. Importantly, the integration of electrochemical and electrical assessments bridges the gap between fundamental structure and

practical application, validating improvements in conductivity, cycling stability, and catalytic activity. Collectively, these findings highlight that substantial use of structural, spectroscopic, and functional characterization to optimize graphene nanosheets for electrochemical and next-generation applications in energy storage, catalysis, and flexible electronics.

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